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ANALYTICAL STUDY AND CONSERVATION PROCESSES OF LATE PERIOD LIMESTONE CANOPIC JAR: CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The canopic jar studied here is from the Grand Egyptian Museum (GEM), Giza, Egypt, and dates back to the Late Period (712-332 B.C). The jar contains bandages of textile contain mummy viscera with resin and black resin blocks. This study aims to use analytical techniques for the isolation and identification of fungi, and the components of the jar, its contents, pigments, previous restoration materials and to evaluate its deterioration aspects. Spectroscopy techniques applied included: optical microscopy (OM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF), X-ray diffraction (XRD), and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). The results revealed that the jar was carved from dolomite limestone, contained red hematite pigment, mastic resin, linen textile bandages, and from earlier adhesive of animal glue and gypsum from previous conservation efforts. The most dominant microbial infection on the jar was the fungi of *Penicillium waksmanii*, *Nigrospora sphaerica*, *Actinomycetes sp* and *Spore-Forming Gram-Positive Bacilli*. Conservation procedures have been applied with high accuracy to conserve the jar including mechanical and chemical cleaning, re-assembling, completion and consolidation.

KEYWORDS: Canopic jar, Viscera, Mummification, Resin, XRD, SEM-EDX, FTIR, Consolidation, Mortar

Figure 1. The studied canopic jar; A: The jar and lid; B: Jar's contents

1. INTRODUCTION: MUMMIFICATION AND CANOPIC JARS

The ancient Egyptians developed mummification processes that included the need to extract all body internal organs, that began in Old Kingdom (Nicholson, et al., 2000). In Middle Kingdom there was perhaps partial removal of the internal organs, and in the New kingdom it has become a basic step where it was extraction of the brain and viscera (Abdel-Maksoud et al., 2001). Two reasons made the ancient Egyptian extracted the internal organs, the first was spiritual, and the second was a technical, that the residual food and fatty visceral tissues have the ability to decompose (Harris et al., 1980). The brain was being removed through the nose or an opening behind the neck (Redford, 2001; Leek, 1969) stomach, internal organs also the contents of the chest cage were removed through an abdominal incision on the left side of the body (Abdel-Maksoud et al., 2001) with a knife of obsidian or other kind of stone (Lauer et al., 1955). The internal organs were dehydrated using natron salt then washed and rinsed out with spices and palm wine (Sivrev et al., 2005); spices as a deodorant and palm wine which have some sterilizing effect (Taconis, 2005), then treated properly to fill pores and prevent moisture (Cockburn, 1998). Each of these organs was then individually wrapped in fabric and placed in a canopic jar each jar held a different organ (Aufderheide, 2003) according to the lid shape. The jar with monkey's head contains the lungs of the mummy (Goff, 1979), while jars contained black resin blocks that were poured inside (Lucas, 1926). The canopic jars appeared in Old kingdom and continued to develop in its shapes until the New Kingdom jar lids were shaped to represent one of the four sons of Horus. Each form is associated with specific member of the viscera (Aufderheide, 2003). Manufacturing of vessels in ancient Egypt started by selecting the appropriate stone

block for the shaping (Mallory, 2000), then the outer outlines of the vessel were determined which show the shape of the vessel (Engelbach, 1961). The vessels were sculptured from the outside using pieces of stones more solid than the vessel, then a hole at the top of the vessel, was made, and using tubular drill an ancient Egyptian tool to empty the internal vessel part (Stocks, 2005). Final stage was polishing the outside body of the vessel and carving the lid of the vessel (Nicholson et al., 2000).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The analytical approaches included Optical Microscopy (OM), Environmental Scanning Electron Microscopy (ESEM), X-ray Diffraction (XRD), X-ray Florescence (XRF) and Fourier transformed infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) were used to indicate the nature of the original and added materials, as well as, to establish the conservation state of the jar.

2.1. Historical background of studied canopic jar

The studied canopic jar dates back to the Late Period (712 - 332 BC), it found in Dera Abu Elnaga area on the west bank of Luxor - Upper Egypt under number (23220) it's provenance was in Egyptian Museum (EM) in Cairo now transported to the Conservation Center of the Grand Egyptian Museum (GEM.CC) with GEM number (22016). The jar consists of two pieces jar and lid, short thick jar with broad base, high shoulder and shallow cavity. The lid in the form of monkey's head with human ears that indicated that the jar contains one of the internal viscera is the lungs of the mummy. Eyebrows, eyelids, pupil and edge of ears colored with black pigment, Iris and ears colored with red pigment. The jar contains black resin blocks and bandages of textile warped the black risen block that contains mummy viscera.

2.2. Visual assessment by digital camera and AutoCAD

Visual assessment, by the critical eye of the team work so, we can determine the aspects of deterioration found on the canopic jar. This is very effective because the causes and mechanism of deterioration may be easily identified. The critical eye of conservator can also determine the appropriate techniques of analysis, which should be used for identifying the condition of the studied jar. To record the changes associated with jar, a high-resolution digital camera image that was used to create realistic photographic documentation of the aspects of deterioration, computer graphic documentation was done using (AutoCAD 2012). With CAD, a map of the damage was made. (Abdel-Maksoud, 2011).

2.3. Optical Microscope (OM)

Optical Microscope (OM) using a Zeiss Stereo DV 20 (stereomicroscope) equipped with Axio Cam MRC5 was used to identify damage with different magnifications.

2.4. Environmental scanning electron microscopy (ESEM)

A Quanta 3D 200i scanning electron microscope made by FEI was used for examining the stone used in the studied jar. The accelerating voltage was 25 kV in the magnification range of 80 to 3000x. The investigation was carried out in both the large filtered detector mode (SSD).

2.5. X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD)

X-ray diffraction using X-ray Diffractometer System PW3040-Analytical Equipment- PANalytical pro model, Cu-target tube and Ni filter at 40 kV and 30MA were used (X'Pert Highscore) software was used for identifying the components of the stone and previous restoration materials.

2.6. X-ray fluorescence analysis portable (XRF)

In order to identify the red pigment found on jar's lid X-Ray fluorescence measurement was carried out with portable system, thermo scientific Niton XL3t analyzer including X-ray tube with Ag anode, 50kV and 0-200 μ A max, at mining mode, spot diameter 3mm, duration of exposure 46.97 seconds.

2.7. Fourier transformed infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

IRPrestige-21 (FTIR spectrophotometer) and the IR solution software in the 400- 4000 cm^{-1} range with

resolution of 8 cm^{-1} were used for identifying the resins, textile and previous adhesive material by comparing the obtained spectra with literature data and standards created in the FTIR laboratory. (Abdel-Maksoud, 2013).

2.8. Isolation and identification of fungi

To identify microbial infection on the canopic jar, some sterilized cotton swabs were used to swab different areas on jar's stone. Nutrient agar and modified Dox agar media was used for the isolation of fungi, then incubated at 30°C for 21 after that the dishes were examined and the growths were isolated separately and purified to obtain the organisms in pure form to complete the experiments. The previously selected isolates were grown on a nutrient specific to the identification. After the incubation period after incubation period microbial slices were made and morphological morphology was determined and compared to standard morphological characteristics according to Domsch et al., (2007). The isolation and identification of microbial infection were achieved at Micro Analytical lab, the Grand Egyptian Museum, Giza, Egypt.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Visual assessment by digital camera and AutoCAD

Through the naked eye observation, it was found deterioration aspects, also the jar stored in bad conditions which led to advanced deterioration. The jar was previously restored with inappropriate materials used in assemblage and completion. Some deterioration aspects were noticed for jar's stone such as dust adhered, dirt, feeble areas, missing parts, scratches, jar warped with metal wire that caused of corrosion stains, spots from adhesive material, breaks (Fig. 2) Presence of resin participated in damage stone whereas frequency of melting and hardening lead firstly to make stress on the stone especially the jar full of resin blocks and wrappings, secondly Separation of parts of stone and sticking to resins blocks, also make black paint layer on the internal part of jar, and it was reason for linen damage. About pigments lost and weakness in its parts. As for the linen wrappings dry, degraded and have missing parts. The condition of the coffin was recorded in detail and each part was carefully recorded using AutoCAD program.

This technique produced clear documentation of the deterioration aspects and making deterioration mapping for the jar as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 2. Aspects of deterioration found in the jar: A- Dust and dirt; B- Missing parts, scratches and classification; C- previous conservation materials (metal wire, completion mortar and adhesive); D- breaks and stains; E- feeble areas, cracks and previous completion mortar; F- missing parts; G- lid covered with black resin; H- part from jar covered from inside with black resin and textile parts.

Figure 3. 2D drawing of the jar showing deterioration aspects; A-the front of jar and showing its dimensions; B- jar from behind; C- the jar left side.

3.2. Identification of stone and diagnosis its condition

XRD spectrum of the stone confirmed the presence of Dolomite limestone where it proved the existence of Calcite (CaCO_3) 80%, Dolomite ($\text{CaMg}(\text{CO}_3)_2$) 10%, and Silica (SiO_2) 10% (Fig.4) and EDAX spectrum of stone sample confirmed XRD where that showed the presence of elements (Ca, Mg, Si, C, O) and also it showed the presence of sulphur (S) that may be the result of the decomposition of some

of the organic material found inside the jar which contains sulphur (S) (Fig 5). Optical microscopic examination showed parts from jar stone and textile has been attached with resin and, also, exhibited deterioration of internal fabric of linen (Fig. 6). Scanning electron microscope has showed stone condition. Presence of fine cracks, gaps and voids resulted weakness of the internal structure of stone, also showed overlap of resin with stone particles (Fig. 7).

Figure 4. XRD analysis of stone sample.

Figure 5. EDAX analysis of stone sample.

Figure 6. Examination of jar by OM. A: C- parts from limestone has been attached with resin (A-10X, B- 25X, C-10X). D- Deterioration of Internal fabric of linen (25X). E- Linen fabric attached with resin (10X). F- Parts of the fabric are damaged and separated (15X).

Figure 7. SEM micrographs of limestone. A. The image tells about the inner texture of the stone and its weakness. B, C. shows there are gaps and spaces in stone structure which causes its weakness. D. It shows the presence of cracks. E. shows overlap of resin with stone components. F. Explains the existence of fossils and remains of fossils and the disintegration of stone crystals.

3.2. Identification of red pigment

Samples could not be taken to identify red and black pigments and binding media. Portable XRF of red pigment showed the presence of (Fe) that suggesting the use of hematite pigment (Fig. 8).

3.3. Identification of jar's contents

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis of risen sample proved that the basic component of the resin is Mastic. This indication based on characteristic absorption bands that

showed in Table 1 and the archaeological sample result was compared with the standard sample (Fig. 9)

Mastic characteristic IR absorption bands are O-H stretching band (3600 - 3200) cm^{-1} , C-H stretching band (3100 - 2800) cm^{-1} , C=O stretching band (1740 - 1640) cm^{-1} , C-C stretching band (1650 - 1600) cm^{-1} , C-H bending band (1480 - 1300) cm^{-1} , C-O stretching bands (1300-900) cm^{-1} (Derrick, et al., 1999).

Figure 8. Characteristic XRF spectrum of red Pigment

Table 1. Characteristic IR absorption bands of mastic and its values.

Functional group	Standard sample Wavelengths(cm^{-1}) (Derrick et al., 1999)	Archaeological sample Wavelengths (cm^{-1})
O-H stretching band	3412	3446
C-H stretching bands	2918	2954 , 2868
C=O stretching band	1708	1705
C-C stretching band	1627	1637
C-H bending bands	1463 , 1377	1458 , 1382
C-O stretching bands	1172 , 1116	1182 , 1111

Figure 9. FTIR spectra for mastic archaeological sample and standard

The infrared spectra of textile sample proved that is Linen (Fig 10.) This indication based on characteristic absorption bands of sample and compares it with standard sample that showed in Table 2.

The results showed that there are changes in the IR spectra of the archaeological sample compared to the spectra of the standard sample (non-decayed sample). By comparing the results, it is evident that there are changes in the region from 1600 to 1750 cm^{-1} for the archaeological sample shows intensive absorption which is caused by stretching vibrations of carbonyl groups (Moha-

patra et al., 2015). This region proved the most convenient for monitoring cellulose degradation. The spectra of cellulose show decrease of bands particularly at 1372 cm^{-1} , 1336 cm^{-1} , 1313 cm^{-1} , 1280 cm^{-1} , 1160 cm^{-1} and 1105 cm^{-1} (Moustafa, et al., 2017; Hulleman, 1994), when moving from high crystalline to amorphous cellulose, which means that the sample is degraded (Mohapatra et al., 2015). Also, two intensive bands with maxima at 2922 cm^{-1} are attributed to deformation vibrations of C-H groups in methyl and methylene groups [CH₃, CH₂, CH₂-OH] belonging to cellulose as well as to lignin (Day et al., 2005).

Table 2. Characteristic IR absorption bands of linen and its values

Functional group	Standard sample Wavelengths(cm^{-1}) (Derrick et al., 1999)	archaeological sample Wavelengths (cm^{-1})
O-H stretching band	3404	3373
C-H stretching bands	2916 , 2899	2922
C-C stretching band	1627	1627
C-H bending bands	1429 , 1375	1429 , 1375

Figure 10. FTIR spectra for linen archaeological sample and standard sample.

3.4. Identification of previous conservation materials

XRD spectrum of the previous completion material confirmed that was Gypsum (Fig. 10), and infrared spectra (FTIR) of previous adhesive proved that it was Animal glue (Fig 11). This indication based on characteristic absorption bands that showed in Table

3. and compares it with standard sample. Characteristic IR absorption bands are: N-H stretching band ($3400\text{-}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$), C-H stretching bands ($3100\text{-}2800\text{ cm}^{-1}$), C=O stretching band ($1660\text{-}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$), C-N-H bending band ($1565\text{ - }1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$), C-H bending band ($1480\text{-}1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$) (Derrick, M.R., et al., 1999).

Figure 11. XRD analysis for gypsum mortar sample.

Table 3. Characteristic IR absorption bands of animal glue and its values

Functional group	Standard sample Wavelengths (cm^{-1}) (Derrick et. Al, 1999).	archaeological sample Wavelengths (cm^{-1})
N-H stretching band	3429	3419
C-H stretching bands	2925, 2863	2926, 2875
C=O stretching band overlapping with N-H: bending band	1623	1653
C-H bending band	1444	1448
C-N stretching band	1240, 1082	1240, 1083
C-H torsion band	936, 871	877

Figure 12. FTIR spectra for adhesive sample.

3.5. Identification of fungi

The studied canopic jar contains organic materials that susceptible to numerous biodeterioration infection which can infect the stone. which cause changes in its physical, chemical, and mechanical properties, and color of stone surfaces. Fungi, the most damaging organisms attacking and even penetrating the surfaces of stone monuments (Ayman et al., 2019) and distort stone shape by causing dark spots appear on stone surface (Bakir et al, 2007; Diakumaku et al., 1995) in addition to its ability to produce organic acids affect the stone (Warscheid et al., 2000). Bacterial infection has distorted effect of stone surface (Konkol et al., 2009). Growth and composition of their colonies leads to mechanical stresses on the internal structure of the stone (Crispim et al., 2004).

Isolation and identification of microbial infection resulted presence of fungi such as *Penicillium waksmanii* and *Nigrospora sphaerica*, also bacteria found

such as *Gram positive short bacilli spore former* and *Actinomyces sp.* (Fig 13.)

Penicillium waksmanii: an anamorph species of the genus of *Penicillium* which was isolated from the alga *Sargassum ringgoldianum*. (John et al., 2007) *Nigrospora sphaerica*: an airborne filamentous fungus in the phylum Ascomycota. It is found in soil, air, and plants as a leaf pathogen. *Actinomyces sp.*: *Actinomyces* is a genus of the Actinobacteria class of bacteria. They are all gram-positive. *Actinomyces* species are facultative anaerobic, and they grow best under anaerobic conditions (Holt, 1994)

Actinomyces species are ubiquitous in soil and in the microbiota of animals, including the human microbiota (Petrova et al., 2015). *Bacilli* refers to a taxonomic class of bacteria. It includes two orders, *Bacillales* and *Lactobacillales*, which contain several well-known pathogens such as *Bacillus anthracis*. All *Bacilli* are gram-positive bacteria (Ludwig, 2015).

Figure 13. A. *Nigrospora sphaerica*. B. *Actinomyces* sp. C. G+Ve Short bacilli spore former

4. CONSERVATION TECHNIQUES USED

The main purpose of Conservation Science is the preservation and restoration of artifacts in such a condition that future generation may experience them and study their value. (Abd-Allah et al., 2016) So different procedures for treating and conserving the studied stone canopic jar were employed. At first before doing any conservation processes we remove jars contents of linen and resin blocks and put it in box of acid free carton.

4.1. Surfaces Cleaning and Removal of previous consolidation materials

FTIR analysis proved that the previous adhesive material was animal glue, and XRD analysis proved that previous completion material was gypsum mortar. Metal wire was removed from the jar. To remove animal glue thin poultice of warm distilled water was impressive in softening animal glue, then using mechanical methods and tools to remove animal glue or reduce its layers, but this did not remove it entirely. So cotton swap immersed in warm distilled water used to remove animal glue from stone surface. Also mechanical methods applied to remove gypsum mortar such as scalpels, spatula, dental

tools and brushes. Soft brushes were used to remove surface dust from jar and lid, after that chemical cleaning was processed to remove the remaining dust, dirt and stains, so cotton swap immersed in distilled water + ethyl alcohol (1:1) was rolled over the surface, and use of ethyl alcohol by brushing to discourage the activity of microorganisms (Fig 14. A-B-C).

4.2. Reassembly of jar parts

After cleaning jar parts edges, 40 % w/v Paraloid B44 in acetone was used for assemblage jar parts.

4.3. Loss completion

Strengthened completion was placed of previous completion mortar of calcium carbonate powder mixed with Acril ME was applied with spatula in missing parts (Fig 14. D).

4.4. Consolidation of feebler stone areas

3% w/v Paraloid B72 in acetone was applied by brush on weak areas to restore to bind weak stone granules, so it provides the object with mechanical strength and physical properties (El-Gohary, 2018).

Figure 14. (A-B) Cleaning processes, C. removing previous adhesive material, D. Complete missing parts

Figure 15. A. The canopic jar before conservation. B. The canopic jar after conservation

5. CONCLUSION

Limestone canopic jar (GEM. No. 22016) dating back to Late period (712-332 B.C.) was found in Dera Abuo Elnaga area on the west bank of Luxor – Upper Egypt, stored in Egyptian museum (EM) then transported to the Grand Egyptian museum. Consisted of jar and monkey's head lid and also containing resin blocks and warping of textile contain mummified organ according jar lid shape the jar contain the lungs of the mummy. Examination and analysis were applied to deep restoring. XRD analysis indicates that the ancient Egypt used Dolomite limestone in carving the jar. FTIR analysis proved that textile wrappings from Linen, and used resin were mainly Mastic. Based to analysis the previous adhesive was animal glue, and the completion material was gypsum mortar. Deterioration aspects including dust, dirt, the jar warped with iron wire, corrosion stains, missing parts, breaks and weakness of stone. Examination result by optical microscope

confirmed that parts from stone and linen separated with resin blocks, degradation of linen fabrics. Digital camera and AutoCad program used for documentation the jar and deterioration aspects. Isolation of microbial resulted proved that fungal and bacterial infection such as *Penicillium waksmanii* and *Nigrospora sphaerica*, also bacteria such as *G+ve short bacilli spore former* and *Actinomycetes sp.* Mechanical cleaning was effective in removing surface dust and previous conservation materials whether adhesive and completion mortar. Chemical cleaning applied to clean attached dust, dirt and stains cotton swap immersed in distilled water + ethyl alcohol (1:1) was rolled over the surface, and use of ethyl alcohol by brushing to discourage the activity of microorganisms. Paraloid B44 was used in assemblage jar parts, Paraloid B72 was effective in consolidate limestone weakness areas, mortar of Acril ME mixed with calcium carbonate powder was used in complete loss parts instead of previous gypsum mortar.

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